

LOW TEMPERATURE MOULDING PREPREG SYSTEMS FOR THE MANUFACTURE OF HIGH TEMPERATURE COMPOSITES MOULD TOOLS AND COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY

This Paper describes a prepreg epoxy resin system with the unusual properties of an initial cure at ambient or mildly elevated temperatures and a heat distortion temperature in excess of 200°C. Low temperature moulding (LTM) prepregs with carbon, aramid and glass reinforcement have been produced and used for the manufacture of both high temperature mould tools and high temperature resistant components. The unusual combination of properties of LTM prepregs has been shown to result in both significant cost savings and improvements in moulding accuracy and performance, particularly in respect of mould tool manufacture.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced fibre reinforced composite materials in the form of carbon, aramid and glass fibre prepregs are now well established in the aerospace industry for the manufacture of high performance lightweight components.

The prepreg resin systems needed to achieve the optimum laminate performance properties over a wide range of temperatures usually require an initial cure at a relatively high temperature (e.g. 175°C). In many cases the composite materials so produced are not required to actually operate at very high temperatures, however a high temperature initial cure of the resin matrix is required to achieve a good retention of component mechanical properties at a more modest temperature (e.g. 80°C). An additional reason for the relatively high initial cure temperatures of many prepreg resin systems is that the prepreg must not deteriorate significantly whilst in low temperature storage.

In contrast to conventional prepreg materials, LTM prepregs can be cured at any temperature above 20°C and subsequently post cured in stages to give a heat distortion temperature in excess of 200°C. Perhaps surprisingly, despite the reactive nature of the prepreg at ambient temperatures or above, the storage life of the prepreg at -18°C is comparable with that of conventional prepregs and is at least 6 months to 1 year. At ambient temperature, LTM prepregs remain workable for two to three days after removal from cold storage and it is generally recommended that the layup procedure should be completed within the first

two days, the third day being reserved for bagging etc. Whilst a two day working life might appear to be short compared with that of most conventional prepregs, it is considerably longer than the pot life of a liquid laminating resin system would allow. Having completed a given layup, the moulding can be simply allowed to cure at ambient temperature under vacuum bag or autoclave consolidation. Typically a six day initial cure is required at ambient temperature before the partially cured moulding has developed sufficient mechanical strength to preclude the possibility of damage after removal from the pattern or mould.

The initial cure time can however, be shortened simply by performing the initial cure at a mildly elevated temperature. Typical cure times at mildly elevated temperatures are three hours at 60°C or twelve hours at 40°C etc. After the initial cure phase is complete, the solid partially cured moulding can be post-cured in stages up to the desired working temperature. The LTM resin system, LTM10, has the unusual property of a heat distortion temperature which steps significantly ahead of the post cure temperature and hence the moulding accuracy can be maintained throughout the entire operation. A typical post-curing procedure, after an initial cure at 20°C, would be two hours at 40°C, then one hour each at 80°C, 120°C, 150°C, 180°C and 200°C for a tool required to operate at 200°C. The maximum permissible operating temperature of laminates manufactured using the LTM10 resin system has not been established, but is certainly at least 200°C.

LTM prepregs are produced with a variety of carbon aramid and glass fibre reinforcement by Advanced Composite Materials Limited, part of the Advanced Composites Group of Companies.

The laminates produced using the LTM resin system possess high fibre volume fractions and low void contents as would be expected from any prepreg and consequently exhibit good mechanical performance and a good retention of mechanical properties at elevated temperatures. Typical test results are shown in table 1.

TEST TEMPERATURE	WARP FLEXURAL STRENGTH		WARP FLEXURAL MODULUS	
	MPa	% RETENTION OF 21°C FLEXURAL STRENGTH	MPa	% RETENTION OF 21°C FLEXURAL MODULUS
21°C	650	100	26000	100
150°C	525	81	23700	91
177°C	455	70	22500	86
200°C	383	59	21500	83

TABLE 1

Flexural Test Results for M7781/LTM10 glass fibre composite.
Fibre Content 52 v/o. Post cured to 180°C.

LTM preregs have been found to offer both cost and performance advantages in two quite distinct applications:-

1. As mould tool materials for the manufacture of conventional hot cured prepreg components.
2. As component materials in their own right.

Each of these applications is discussed below:

Mould Tool Manufacture for Composite Components

Various characteristics required of a mould tool for high temperature curing prepreg components were examined in reference 1. It was concluded that a mould tool should ideally produce:-

Components which are dimensionally accurate.

Possess a good surface finish.

Be completely impermeable under autoclave use conditions.

Be capable of withstanding several hundred autoclave cures without degradation of surface finish, loss of gas tightness or distortion.

Possess a low thermal mass in order to minimise energy consumption and to allow faster ramping and cooling times during component cures.

Possess thermal expansion coefficients identical to those of the components to be cured on them.

Be cost effective to produce.

The various tooling routes available for the production of high temperature mould tools were examined in some detail in reference 1 and the merits of each route in respect of the performance parameters listed above was qualitatively assessed. The routes examined were LTM prepreg, conventional hot cured prepreg, wet layup, nickel electrodeposition, NC machined graphite, NC machined aluminium alloy and NC machined steel. The various stages involved in each of these tooling routes is summarised in figure 1. With the exception of those tooling routes where the tool is machined from a solid billet of material, all require the manufacture of some form of pattern or master model from which it is required to produce a mould tool capable of operating for long periods at a relatively high temperature. Thus, with the LTM prepreg route and the wet layup route, the tool is moulded directly against a low cost master model or pattern of wood, plaster or cured foam and subsequently removed from the pattern and post cured in stages up to the desired working temperature.

In the case of the hot cured prepreg tooling route, since a wood or plaster pattern would be incapable of withstanding the high initial cure temperatures of the prepreg, it is necessary to manufacture a high temperature duplicate of the master model using at least two "throwaway" intermediate moulding stages which both add to the cost of the tool manufacturing procedure and can also result in a loss of accuracy owing

TOOLING ROUTE	THERMAL EXPANSION COMPATIBILITY	WEIGHT	THERMAL MASS	TOOL LIFE AT HIGH TEMPERATURE	STABILITY/ ACCURACY	COST EFFECTIVENESS	TOTAL RATING
LTM PREPREG	*****	*****	*****	***	*****	****	27
HOT-CURED PREPREG	*****	*****	*****	***	****	**	24
WET LAYUP	****	****	****	*	***	*****	21
NICKEL ELECTRODEPOSITION	** ¹	**	**	****	**	**	14
N.C. MACHINED ALUMINIUM ALLOY	*	**	**	****	*	**	12
N.C. MACHINED STEEL	**	*	*	*****	**	*	12
N.C. MACHINED BULK GRAPHITE	***	*	*	**	***	*	11

***** Excellent **** Very good *** Good ** Fair * Poor

1 Thermal expansion compatibility = fair for carbon fibre or aramid fibre composite components, poor for glass fibre composite components.

TABLE 2
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF ALTERNATIVE TOOLING ROUTES FOR HIGH TEMPERATURE CURING COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

to the progressive build up of tolerances with each moulding operation. Similarly, in the case of the nickel electrodeposition route, a traditionally manufactured pattern is unsuitable for immersion in a plating bath and hence a duplicate of the original master model is again made by the means of two intermediate moulding stages, this duplicate being referred to as the bath or plating master, against which the nickel coating is deposited. Thus again, the additional moulding stages involved in the manufacture of nickel tooling constitute an additional cost and can potentially lead to a loss of moulding accuracy.

The NC machining of tools from bulk graphite aluminium alloy or steel offers the possibility of eliminating the need for a master model, however, the cost of this operation is generally very high.

In terms of the performance of tools manufactured using the various routes shown in figure 1 all exhibit a satisfactory tool life of perhaps several hundred component cures with the exception of the wet layup tooling route where the relatively low and variable fibre content and high void content of the tool frequently limits the maximum working life. Since the composite components to be cured on the mould tool generally have directionally variable (and in the case of carbon or aramid components near zero) thermal expansion characteristics, it is highly desirable that the mould tool should possess identical thermal expansion characteristics. In practice only composite tooling offers the possibility of exactly matching expansion characteristics of tooling component and hence allowing tooling component to be manufactured to net size.

In respect of the thermal mass of the mould tools, composite tooling of whatever form is far superior to any of the alternative tooling materials. The great advantage of tooling of low thermal mass is that relatively little energy is expended in heating the tool and much faster ramping and overall cure times can be achieved with a vast improvement in component turn round time.

A qualitative assessment of the merits of each tooling route is given in table 2. Whilst the relative importance of each of the assessment parameters used will clearly vary from application to application, it is nevertheless clear that only prepreg composite tooling is satisfactory in every respect. It is also clear from the qualitative assessment given that the LTM process by simply eliminating the need for an elevated temperature and initial cure offers all of the advantages inherent to prepreg tooling but at a lower overall cost and with a potentially improved level of accuracy.

Tool Manufacture Using LTM Prepregs

The LTM process essentially provides a method for producing high temperature resistant composite tooling directly from a low cost master model or pattern in a single moulding operation. Any desired master model material can be used, including wood or splined plaster, providing that the model possesses vacuum integrity.

After having applied a suitable release agent to the pattern, LTM prepreg may be applied a layer at a time until the desired laminate thickness is achieved. For ease of handling, each layer of the laminate

is often formed from pre-cut square or rectangles of prepreg which are butt jointed. Butt joints in adjacent layers being staggered by at least 15mm. One or more vacuum de-bulking/de-gasing operations are usually carried out at intermediate stages during the layup in order to avoid bridging in female corners, to achieve good consolidation and to avoid other problems such as wrinkling.

LTM tooling prepregs are usually supplied in the form of bi-directional fabrics, typical details are given in table 3. In the case of a carbon fibre LTM tool, a surfacing ply of 2 x 2 twill weave prepreg is used and then the bulk of the laminate made up from plies of a heavier weight 4 x 4 twill weave fabric. A final ply of the 2 x 2 twill weave fabric is then applied in order to ensure a mid plane symmetric stacking sequence. This is most important in order to ensure that the cured laminate exhibits no bending extensional coupling and hence will not undergo out of plane bending distortion when the tool is raised in temperature.

In addition, it is necessary to avoid processing conditions which could lead to laminate asymmetry such as the practice of bleeding excess resin from one side of the laminate. For this reason, with the exception of the surfacing ply which normally has a relatively high resin content in order to achieve a perfect surface finish, LTM prepregs are designed to be cured under minimum or zero bleed conditions.

Ideally, the fibre orientations within a mould tool should be such as to give in-plane thermal expansion characteristics identical to those of the components to be cured on the tool. In practice however, it is found that the expansion co-efficients of most practical multi-directional laminate fall within a fairly narrow range. Figure 2 shows a plot of the 0° in-plane thermal expansion co-efficient for the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ $\pm 45^\circ$ family of carbon fibre composite laminates as predicted by classical lamination theory.

It can be seen from figure 2 that the expansion coefficients of all but the most extreme of layups fall within a relatively narrow band and that a tool with a quasi-isotropic layup will possess expansion characteristics which match very closely the vast majority of component layups, providing of course that the fibre types and volume fractions of the tool and component are similar. Since it is easy to produce LTM laminates with the correct volume fraction of reinforcing fibre using bi-directional fabrics and since this weave configuration permits a quasi-isotropic layup to be achieved, it may be concluded that tools produced using this layup configuration will have expansion coefficients which match very closely those of all but the most extreme of component layups irrespective of whether these components are themselves manufactured from uni-directional plies or bi-directional fabrics.

After having completed the layup of the tool shell, it is bagged and prepared for autoclave or vacuum bag cure. Ideally, an autoclave pressure of 0.6 MPa (90lb/in²) should be used in order to achieve a perfect tool surface finish, in which case it is usually desirable to accelerate the initial cure by raising the temperature to 40°C or above. If a vacuum bag cure is to be used, some slight pitting of the tool surface may be visible, however the surface finish will in general still be acceptable.

TABLE 3

LTM PRE-PREGS FOR TOOLING APPLICATIONS

Weave Style	Dry Cloth Weight (g/m ²)	Nominal Thickness (mm)	Warp	Weft	Resin	Nominal Fibre Content by Volume	Roll Width (m)
<u>Carbon Fibre Pre-pregs</u>							
CFS 001 4 x 4 Twill	280	0.31	T300-3000 x 40B or equivalent	T300-3000 x 40B or equivalent	LTM10	55%	1.25
CFS 003 2 x 2 Twill	199	0.23	T300-3000 x 40B or equivalent	T300-3000 x 40B or equivalent	LTM10	45%	0.98
<u>Glass Fibre Pre-pregs</u>							
GFS 001 8 Harness Satin	302	0.25	22 ends/cm E Glass	21.3 ends/cm E Glass	LTM10	45%	1.02
GFS 002 8 Harness Satin	849	0.65	16.5 ends/cm E Glass	13.8 ends/cm E Glass	LTM10	50%	0.98

After the initial cure has been carried out, the solid, partially cured tool may be removed from the pattern and post-cured in stages up to its desired working temperature as described above. Most support structures may be made from either solid laminated composite board or honeycomb panelling and should be manufactured using the same fibrous reinforcement as the mould shell in order to ensure thermal compatibility. The support structure should be designed to support the self weight of the mould tool and component and may or may not be permanently attached to the tool itself. If it is desired to permanently attach the support frame to the tool, wet laminated cleats may be used for this purpose.

Prepreg Tool Performance and Accuracy

Any prepreg mould tool should give satisfactory performance for several hundred elevated temperature autoclave component cures without degradation of surface finish, loss of gas tightness or distortion taking place. The high initial cure temperatures of conventional prepregs however, can and do introduce a system of residual stresses within the laminate comprising the tool during the tool manufacturing process. If relatively thermally inert fibres such as carbon are used, the stresses present in the resin matrix upon cooling from a high initial cure temperature will generally be tensile in sense. It is well established that these residual stresses are a major potential source of matrix micro-cracking in laminated composite components.

Whilst such micro-cracking has been shown to have negligible effect upon the mechanical performance of laminates, there is some evidence that composite tools can develop leak paths within individual layers or tows when used under autoclave conditions and hence it is possible that the presence or otherwise of micro-cracks may be a significant factor in determining the maximum tool life of a given prepreg tool.

Since with LTM prepregs however, the initial cure is carried out at a relatively low temperature, the magnitude of the thermal stresses upon cooling from the initial cure temperature is generally extremely small or even zero. Moreover, when an LTM carbon fibre composite laminate is raised in temperature, the residual stress system within the resin matrix will in general be compressive in nature rather than tensile. Thus, the elimination of a field of residual matrix tensile stresses in LTM laminates by virtue of the low temperature initial cure can be shown to eliminate a major potential source of micro-cracking and any resulting permeability problems.

An additional consequence of the relatively high initial cure temperatures of conventional prepreg mouldings and the resulting residual stress system produced thereby, is the distortion of mouldings during or after the curing process, a common example of which is the flange spring-in of a carbon fibre composite channel section moulding after an elevated temperature cure as shown in figure 3.

The conventional method of eliminating this kind of distortion in components such as combat aircraft wing spars is to incorporate a spring-in allowance for the component into the mould tool. Clearly, if the mould tool itself is to be manufactured from hot curing prepreg materials, it too will spring-in after manufacture, requiring that the

master model (or replica) itself must incorporate an allowance for the combined spring-in of the mould tool and the components.

Since spring-in is predominantly (but not exclusively) a thermal effect, it is not too surprising that ambient or low elevated temperature cured LTM mouldings can be produced with very low or zero spring-in distortion. Thus in addition to the obvious improvement in accuracy which can be made by replacing a multi-splash tooling route with a single moulding operation, LTM prepreg mouldings can also be used to achieve a further improvement in accuracy by the elimination of spring-in and other thermally related distortion phenomena.

Component Manufacture Using LTM Prepregs

Whilst LTM prepregs have been shown to have considerable cost and performance advantages for the manufacture of mould tools for conventional hot curing prepreg components, the materials can themselves be used for component manufacture. The mechanical properties of LTM laminates are superior to and more consistent than those of wet laminated components and compare favourably with those of other hot cured prepreg components. Moreover, the retention of mechanical properties at elevated temperatures is very good, as shown in table 1.

The use of LTM prepregs as component materials offers a cost advantage in that the low initial cure temperatures allow the use of low temperature, low cost mould tools. Since at the low initial cure temperature there is no requirement to match the thermal expansion characteristics of the tooling and component, virtually any mould tool material can be used, including wood or plaster. The extremely short cure cycle times which can be achieved using LTM prepregs at mildly elevated temperatures (e.g. 15 minutes at 90°C) offer the possibility for very short component turnround times which are well suited to high volume production processes such as press moulding.

The considerable improvement in moulding accuracy which can be achieved using LTM prepregs, primarily by virtue of the lower temperature initial cure is potentially very attractive for applications such as radar and communications reflector dishes.

The Advanced Composite Group has used LTM prepregs for the manufacture of components in a wide variety of industrial applications over several years.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has described a low temperature curing prepreg resin system with a high temperature end-use capability and examined the application of prepregs based on this resin system to the manufacture of both mould tools and components. LTM prepregs have been shown to offer significant cost and performance advantages over alternative tool manufacturing processes for composite components, particularly in respect of the level of dimensional accuracy which can be achieved.

The use of a low initial cure temperature has been shown to allow the elimination of matrix tensile residual stress systems inherent to hot cured prepreg mouldings and it is postulated that the elimination of

matrix micro-cracking could lead to an enhancement in tool life at elevated temperatures compared to that achievable with conventional hot cured prepreg tools.

The elimination of distortion phenomena such as spring-in in prepreg mouldings by use of the LTM process has been identified as advantageous for both mould tool and component manufacture and it is suggested that this improvement will be of particular value in applications such as the manufacture of radar and communications reflector dishes.

REFERENCES

1. C. Ridgard, Low Temperature Curing Prepreg Systems for High Temperature Resistant High Performance Composite Mould Tools and Components. Proceedings 8th Int. Conference SAMPE European Chapter Leveaux, France. May 1987

FIGURE 1 KEY STAGES IN THE VARIOUS HIGH TEMPERATURE TOOLING ROUTES FOR COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

FIGURE 2 0° THERMAL COEFFICIENT OF THERMAL EXPANSION FOR THE $0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ FAMILY OF LAMINATES

FIGURE 3 SPRING-IN DISTORTION OF COMPOSITE MOULDINGS

FIGURE 4 LTM CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE TOOL FOR THE BAe ATP AIRLINER